

Towards An Effective Human-Robot Team Collaboration: A Resilient Task Scheduling Approach For Real Industrial Scenarios

Andrea Pupa^{1,2}, Wietse Van Dijk¹, Christiaan Brekelmans¹ and Cristian Secchi²

¹ The Netherlands Organisation for applied scientific research - TNO, The Netherlands

Email: wietse.vandijk@tno.nl, christiaan.brekelmans@tno.nl

² Department of Sciences and Methods of Engineering - University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy

Email: andrea.pupa@unimore.it, cristian.secchi@unimore.it

Abstract—Dynamic task scheduling between human and robots is one of the great challenges of collaborative robotics. The high dynamism of the shared workspace brings many uncertainties that cannot be foreseen on beforehand. Therefore, an offline task scheduling strategy leads to really poor performance in such contexts. In this paper, an approach to achieve a resilient and reliable task scheduling is presented. The proposed framework can deal with deviations during operation, different operator skills, errors and substitution of actors.

Index Terms—Human-robot collaboration, human-centered robotics, task planning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial applications where human and robot work closely together are becoming the new paradigm of industrial settings. Collaborative robots can take over repetitive, challenging or dangerous tasks improving the well-being of the operators [1]. The task allocation problem can be initially solved offline during the design phase, in order to obtain a nominal schedule. Several strategies are already available in literature, e.g. [2], [3] which allow to find the best nominal schedule solving an optimization problem.

Even if optimal, an offline task schedule cannot guarantee a great collaboration. Indeed, during the execution, deviations from the nominal behavior may happen and the nominal schedule performs poorly. Firstly, it may happen that some actors are not available, e.g., the robot has been dispatched. Secondly, the interdependence of tasks must be taken into account to ensure good parallelism. Thirdly, the differences between the various operators, such as their skills or preferences, must be considered to adapt the schedule at runtime. Lastly, there is always the possibility of failures in the execution.

In [4] an integrated task allocation and task scheduling strategy is proposed. The tasks are firstly allocated offline exploiting a two-level feedforward optimization. Then, the tasks are re-allocated online with a mutual trust based procedure.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 818087 (ROSSINI) and SMITZH (the smart industry hub of the greater Rotterdam – The Hague area) coordinated by InnovationQuarter and is supported by Rotterdam-The Hague Metropolitan Region, the Province of South Holland and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy.

Similarly, in [5] the authors propose a two-layer dynamic rescheduling framework, where online rescheduling procedure is based on the real human execution time. Furthermore, the differences between the human operators are embedded in the task allocation process. These proposed strategies, however, are unable to handle most situations that may occur in a real HRC scenario at the same time, making them unsuitable for the industry.

This paper proposes a novel approach towards an effective HRC. The framework exploits a database to understand how the collaborative job is composed. Then, at runtime, it monitors the task execution to understand the human operator skills and the task result and adapt the schedule accordingly. The main contributions of this paper are:

- A novel adaptive task scheduling framework that is effective and applicable to most of the situations that may happen in a collaborative scenario, i.e., suitable for a real industrial application.
- The validation of the proposed framework in several variants, one for each situation, of the same experimental scenario, proving the effectiveness of the framework.

The architecture and a discussions are presented below, while a detailed version can be found in [6].

II. DYNAMIC SCHEDULING ARCHITECTURE

In this paper, a situation where a human operator H and a robot R collaborate to perform a job composed by a set of tasks is considered. The two agents have a pre-defined task distribution which is defined by a set of nominal task schedules. This nominal schedule can be precomputed exploiting strategies already available in literature, e.g. [7], [8].

An effective representation of a general collaborative job can be achieved with an AND/OR graph $\mathcal{G} = (T, E)$, where each node represents the task T_i while each directed edge E_{ij} represents the precedence constraint, i.e. the parent task T_i must be executed after child task T_j . Multiple unlinked edges sharing the same parent model an OR constraint, imposing that the parent task can be executed only if at least one of the children has been completed. The OR constraint can be exploited to define multiple paths that lead from the same

Fig. 1: The overall architecture.

starting point to the same end point, namely *equivalent paths*. The first tasks that belong to equivalent paths are defined as *equivalent tasks*. Multiple edges that share the same parent and they are connected with an arc represent an AND constraint, imposing that the parent task can be executed only if all the children have been completed. The work is considered completed if and only if the final task is performed, which means that some tasks may not have been completed.

The proposed framework is shown in Figure 1, where different components may be distinguished:

- The *Database* block is responsible of storing all the information regarding the tasks, through the *Task Details* block, and evaluating all the required metrics, through the *Data Evaluation* block.
- The *Scheduler* block takes care of choosing the most suitable task for each actor online, considering the human operator capabilities and the parallelism in the collaborative job.
- The *Task Monitoring* block communicates to the Database if the task has been completed or, in case of failure, it gives information about the error in order to schedule a proper recovery action.
- The *Human Capabilities* block exploits the result of the data analysis to estimate the human operator capabilities and knowledge.

The overall procedure starts offline designing the AND/OR graph and inserting all the tasks information inside the database, i.e., its description, the actor that must perform it, the AND/OR constraints and the minimal required expertise level. Subsequently the scheduler choose, for each actor, the tasks over the AND/OR graph that best suit the current scenario. For example, the equivalent paths may be exploited to define paths for different skill levels of the operator and the scheduler chooses the path of the highest admissible level. Once a task has been selected, it is sent to the respective actor. From this point, the task monitoring block starts to continuously check when a task has been concluded and what its result is, i.e. success or error. This information is stored inside the database and used for two different purpose: choose a proper set of recovery tasks, in case of error, and to update the human operator expertise level. In particular, errors are classified into two categories: 1) *Restorable Error*, which does not preclude

the task and requires a set of restoring actions before retrying the execution. 2) *Non-Restorable Error*, which precludes the task execution and requires to execute another task to continue the job. Lastly, the scheduler is triggered again to assign another task, until the collaborative job is concluded.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed framework has been experimentally validated in a human-robot collaborative assembly job, where the human operator collaborates with a Franka Emika Panda, a 7-DoF collaborative robot. In particular, the experiments focused on four different situations: 1) Different human operator skills. 2) Substitution of human actions with robot action. 3) Error handling. 4) Parallelism of the actors with resource sharing. The experiments prove that the proposed framework handles most the situations that may occur in a industrial setting, making the approach highly reliable and applicable to real industrial scenarios. Differently from other approaches like [5] where the robot can not recover the errors. In fact, thanks to its flexibility, the framework can make the most out of HRC not only for an assembly case, but for any collaborative robotics application, such as production lines or automatic machine tending¹. A more depth presentation can be found in the accompanying video.

Future works aim at improving the scheduling strategy in order to also choose the path that optimizes a desired cost function. Moreover, the framework should be tested in user study that involves a real-world industrial scenario. This would lead to a further validation and improvement of the overall framework. Lastly, the framework could be extended to also handle the synchronization between the actors.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Pham, R. Madhavan, L. Righetti, W. Smart, and R. Chatila, "The impact of robotics and automation on working conditions and employment," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 126–128, 2018.
- [2] K. Li, Q. Liu, W. Xu, J. Liu, Z. Zhou, and H. Feng, "Sequence planning considering human fatigue for human-robot collaboration in disassembly," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 83, pp. 95–104, 2019.
- [3] A. Ayough, M. Zandieh, and F. Farhadi, "Balancing, sequencing, and job rotation scheduling of a u-shaped lean cell with dynamic operator performance," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, p. 106363, 2020.
- [4] S. M. Rahman and Y. Wang, "Mutual trust-based subtask allocation for human–robot collaboration in flexible lightweight assembly in manufacturing," *Mechatronics*, vol. 54, pp. 94–109, 2018.
- [5] A. Pupa, W. Van Dijk, and C. Secchi, "A human-centered dynamic scheduling architecture for collaborative application," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 4736–4743, 2021.
- [6] A. Pupa, W. Van Dijk, C. Brekelmans, and C. Secchi, "A resilient and effective task scheduling approach for industrial human-robot collaboration," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 13, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/13/4901>
- [7] L. H. De Mello and A. C. Sanderson, "A correct and complete algorithm for the generation of mechanical assembly sequences," in *1989 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE Computer Society, 1989, pp. 56–57.
- [8] A. Pupa and C. Secchi, "A safety-aware architecture for task scheduling and execution for human-robot collaboration," in *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2021, pp. 1895–1902.

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nCTmw5rmxcc&list=PLqdlkko4UMEjVcNcxhDEFsQetHcPfnlr>